

Seven Questions on Agency: Insights from a systematic-narrative review of sustainability transformations research

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Abstract

The conceptualization of agency for the purpose of sustainability transformation research remains a pivotal yet elusive subject, requiring to capture the inherent interactive complexity of the agent's individual attributes and their socio-material embeddedness while providing enough clarity for empirical applicability. While significant advancements have been made in conceptualizing agency in recent years, the discourse has been characterized as scattered, using inconsistent terminology and drawing on ambiguous analytical lenses. This paper addresses these issues by providing a systematic-narrative review of the literature up to the year 2023 around concepts of agency in sustainability transformation research. On the basis of 157 included articles, three central conceptual claims are made to bring the debate forward: *First*, seven questions on agency are put forward as a theoretical tool to structure both past and future debate on agency, discussing the state of the art of definition, source of agency, relationships to transformative change, structure, power, determinants of actions' qualitative characteristics as well as theoretical foundations. *Second*, a typology of prototypical perspectives on agency is proposed, distinguishing between singular, embedded, and relational/emergent agency approaches. *Third*, drawing on insights from the systematic literature review as well as from discussions in sociology (Giddens, Archer, Emirbayer & Mische, Sewell), it is suggested to bring particularly singular and embedded agency perspectives constructively together by conceptualizing agency as the capability of an agent to perform intentional action (as a result of some reflective deliberation) within specific spatio-temporal contexts.

Keywords: agency, sustainability transformations, sustainability transitions, transformative change, intentionality

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1. Introduction

"Action depends upon the capability of the individual to 'make a difference' to a pre-existing state of affairs or course of events." (Anthony Giddens, 1984, p. 14)

"In failing to recognize the agency of both human and nonhuman actors, such a view makes struggle and contingency invisible and produces nihilism, nostalgia, and ultimately paralysis." (Jenny Odell, 2023, p. 115)

To envision a society that is better equipped to deal with the multidimensional challenges of sustainability concerns it is inevitable to ask critically: What can be done? Leading more specifically to: *What can an agent do, within their very situation, to actually enact meaningful change?* This is because ultimately, any purposeful transformation towards sustainability must be driven by agents, whose (inter-)actions aggregate and multiply to effect substantial shifts in collective ways of doing. Wherever sustainability transformation or transition¹ is required to take place, some agents *must* act deliberately and differently from the status quo to make change happen, i.e., via performing some degree of agency. As researchers, if we underestimate this simple fact, the analysis of change is a purely absent and descriptive one of phenomena in which agents are rendered passive and instrumental, without agency, led mostly by pressures, forces, incidents and their immediate intuitive reactions to them.

Following this argument when thinking about transformative change, agency has to come into play not only as a factor for change as has been regularly suggested (Grin et al., 2011; Wiek et al., 2012; Koistinen et al., 2018), but one of the fundamental units of analysis. It has often been pointed out that sustainability transformation research comes from more systemic perspectives (Fischer & Newig, 2016; Wittmayer et al., 2017) and developed more structural, higher-level theories, regularly based on the multi-level-perspective (MLP) (Geels, 2002) in socio-technical systems research (STS) (Smith et al., 2005; Fuenfschilling & Truffer, 2014; Upham et al., 2021), or Hollings' adaptive cycle (Holling, 1986, 2001) and broader resilience theory in socio-ecological systems research (SES) (Westley et al., 2013; Adams, 2021). However, in the last decade, a shift towards theorizing and empirically researching agency more prominently has occurred (Teerikangas et al., 2021; Kok, 2023).

Although much asked for, theorizing on agency is and always has been controversial and highly diverse, not only in transformation research (as concluded in Fischer & Newig, 2016; Koistinen & Teerikangas, 2021) but also in sociology (e.g., Giddens, 1984; Sewell, 1992; Archer, 1995, 2000; Emirbayer & Mische, 1998; Barnes, 2000) and philosophical thought (Schlosser, 2019; Ferrero, 2021). While Luca Ferrero (2021), editor of the Routledge Handbook of Philosophy of Agency, indicates "a rough-and-ready definition – agency as the capacity to do things or make things happen" (p. 3), he decidedly emphasizes that such a definition does not really say much, and there is *no one right definition*, but more different "pictures of agency"² (ibid., p. 8), essentially hinting at the pertinent riddle of understanding action per se.

¹ Where the distinction is not important, it is subsumed by sustainability transformation research.

² Ferrero (2022) sketches his impression of four different foundational understandings of agency in the philosophy of agency: agency as creation, agency as self-constitution, agency as psychological

Based on the enduring criticisms of STS research, particularly the MLP being unclear w.r.t. agency (Smith et al., 2005; Genus & Coles, 2008; Pesch, 2015), as well as some more tentative critiques for SES research (Folke et al., 2005; Head, 2010), various advancements have emerged with concepts such as institutional work (Lawrence & Suddaby, 2006; Fuenfschilling & Truffer, 2016), transformative agency (Westley et al., 2013), leadership-based concepts (Gram-Hanssen, 2021; Strasser et al., 2022), value-based theories (Sarid & Goldman, 2021) or integrated notions of distributed agency (Enfield & Kockelman, 2017; Engez et al., 2021). Additionally, the development of notable novel theories of agency is ongoing, such as pragmatic transactionalism as a practice-based form of agency theory (De Roeck & Van Poeck, 2023) or fractal agency as a value-based relational approach (O'Brien et al., 2023). Furthermore, a new and highly diverse strand of theory on non-human agency, often being rooted in actor-network theory, has emerged (e.g. Arora et al., 2023; Contesse et al., 2021; Jokinen et al., 2021; Kok et al., 2021), arguing for a highly generalized understanding of agency away from questions of human intentionality.

However, although this diversity and novelty in approaches keeps the debate lively, it makes communication across sub-disciplines, as well as general comparability, challenging. Koistinen & Teerikangas' (2021) conclude in their descriptive systematic review "that the conceptualizations of agency remain scattered" (p. 12) and there is "a need for more conceptual clarity and coherence" (p. 22).

Echoing this concern, the goal of the present *systematic but decidedly narrative* review (see Section 2) is to not only make navigating agency research easier but also to enable future research to be better situated within the diversity of existing and partially contradicting approaches, allowing a more cumulative gain of knowledge. While this can be seen as a continuation of existing reviews on actors and agency in the sustainability transitions literature (Fischer & Newig, 2016; Koistinen & Teerikangas, 2021) as well as tangentially a recent review on agency on corporate sustainability transformations (Buhr et al., 2023), the approach taken here is more critical-interpretative and less quantitative-descriptive.

Scope and Research Questions

Arguably, agency is always conceptually involved when we examine agents and their actions. Therefore, a review attempting to cover most agency-related research in the field would need to entail all studies focussing on different types of actors/agents and their types of actions, since all this literature may address agency without naming it as such. However, this is hardly feasible and may also require a predefined understanding of what agency actually is and is not. Hence, the scope of this review cannot be agency as such, but more agency as a concept (or label) and directly related theoretical or empirical implications (see what the search string does and does not entail listed in Section 2.2 Literature Search).

To make the scope specific, this review attempts to mainly shed light on the following research questions:

causality, and agency as reason responsiveness. Delving deeper into these different paradigms may be useful for a strong theoretical foundation of agency for transformation research, since particularly philosophical perspectives are largely overlooked in this field.

1. *What research is conducted and which conceptual questions are raised under the label “agency” in the context of both sustainability transition and transformation research? How can the debate be structured?*
2. *What are conceptualizations of agency in both sustainability transitions and transformations research?*
3. *How can the various concepts of agency be synthesized into something like a typology of agency perspectives?*

This paper is structured as follows. In Section 2, the literature gathering and analysis method is described, followed by the reporting of descriptive results in Section 3. In Section 0, a brief review of some key theoretical roots is presented, followed by the presentation of main interpretative results in Section 5, namely three prototypical agency perspectives and a coding scheme of seven questions on the agency. Section 6 entails a general discussion and a proposition for an expanded agency definition tailored to singular and embedded agency approaches before Section 7 draws some conclusions.

2. Methods

2.1 What type of systematic review is needed?

Systematic literature reviews are based on a method to make transparent not only the literature search but also the literature selection and analysis processes as far as possible (Page et al., 2021). This allows readers to better assess the scope, focus, and overall quality of the review (Petticrew & Roberts, 2006). However, there is, particularly when considering theory and qualitative data from social sciences, a limit to this, since the authors' subjectivity is particularly involved in the interpreting of the literature (even when applying preconceived coding mechanisms). There is also a risk of putting too much emphasis on the seemingly 'objective' quantification of results (i.e. reviews leaning more to attempting meta-analyses where arguably unsuitable for the research question at hand), or decontextualization, particularly when theory or diverse contexts are involved, uprooting the key results from their conditions (Dixon-Woods, 2010). This risk is especially present, when trying to bring together research stemming from very different disciplines and paradigms, and hence is particularly relevant for a review on agency in sustainability transformation research.

The systematic review done here can be labeled as a configurative (Gough et al., 2012) or narrative one (Turnbull et al., 2023) with the main aim of understanding the development of research in the field, making comparisons and synthetically deriving some form of theory or conceptual advancement from these results. The type stands in between 'classic' systematic reviews and meta-analyses common in the medical sciences or psychology which follow completely a strict analysis- and reporting procedure (such as PRISMA, see Page et al., 2021) and on the other extreme 'traditional' narrative reviews which in the past typically did not specify how literature included was found, selected and interpreted at all (Ferrari, 2015).

2.2 Literature Search

Due to the nature of the research questions, the search string used has been straight forward and did not require many iterative processes. Since the focus is on agency concepts in sustainability transitions *and* transformations research, both terms were included in the

search. Existing systematic reviews on agency (Fischer & Newig, 2016; Koistinen & Teerikangas, 2021) only use the term *transition*, limiting the scope quite significantly. The final search string was “agency” AND sustainab* AND (transition* OR transformat*) yielding 1664 results in Web of Science Core Collection and Scopus, after removing duplicates (see Figure 1). This is basically an extension of Fischer & Newig’s (2016) search string.³

2.3 Screening Process

Figure 1 illustrates the literature search, screening, and selection process. All bibliographical entries and abstracts from the Web of Science and Scopus literature search were exported, and duplicates were removed. The yielded 1664 results underwent a title-abstract screening process, categorizing them as excluded, pending, or likely included based on the following criteria:

- 1) *The publication makes some contribution to the theoretical or empirical understanding of agency – while addressing it as such, and*
- 2) *the publication is concerned with sustainability transition or transformation processes.*

A publication was deemed irrelevant if it did not suffice both criteria. After the first round of title-abstract screening, all pending results were screened again based on the abstract or, if necessary, based on full-paper text, and were either excluded or went into the likely included category, resulting in 383 likely included papers. For these papers, all full-paper texts were checked to make a final decision on inclusion for theoretical analysis. Records were coded as highly, medium, low relevant, or irrelevant during this process. The degree of relevancy (low, medium, high) was judged based on how substantially the research was concerned with understanding agency (criterion 1). Publications with low relevancy tackled agency only tangentially or indirectly and were mainly concerned with other concepts or topics. The final corpus of included literature contained 157 results, with 71 coded as highly relevant and 86 as medium relevant (see full literature list in supplementary materials).

³ Some alternatives were considered, such as including specific agent concepts such as entrepreneur, incumbent, niche agent or change agent. However, it was not intended to reduce the scope further since then hardly a general claim on agency research could be made, nor to broaden it further due to limited resources (e.g. by adding the agent concepts as a disjunction as part of the agency conjunction term).

Figure 1. Flow chart of the search and screening process, following PRISMA (Page et al., 2021).

2.4 Analysis and Interpretation Process

The analysis and interpretation process involved two rounds of reading and coding. The *first round* of analysis entailed reading approx. 50% of included articles and was performed as an inductive coding approach. The goal was here to get an overview of the literature, collecting and listing for each paper the central research focus, agency definition, theoretical backgrounds, empirical context (if applicable) and overall themes.⁴ Based on this first explorative analysis, a detailed 'questioning scheme' was developed involving *seven questions* to structure the debate and different perspectives, concepts, and empirical evidence. The slightly adapted scheme is a central result of the analysis and will be reported and discussed in Section 5.2 Seven Questions on Agency.

After the first round of reading, analysis, and the development of the questioning scheme, a second round followed in which this scheme was used as an analytical and interpretative tool. Each paper was questioned on the basis of this scheme, and respective answers were derived, listed, and categorized. The analysis remained open during this phase to change or add questions, but no significant changes were made, except that two separate questions were collapsed to one.

⁴ Only literature from 2022 and before and from the Web of Science Core Collection could be considered for the first, explorative coding phase, since an updated search including Scopus and literature published in 2023 has been conducted just in late January 2024.

3. Descriptive Results

The main quantitative descriptive results can be viewed in *Figure 2*. It shows the lists of top journals and edited volumes for included publications⁵, a graph for the results yielded by the search string per year in the research database Scopus, illustrating a significant yearly growth of publications captured by the search string, and the prevalence of defining agency as a term. Notably, almost half of the coded as high relevance and three-quarters of the coded as medium relevance publications do not provide a clear definition of agency (either none at all or only implicitly as, e.g., revealed in examples or if referring to literature).

Further, *Figure 3* shows a heuristic depiction of different theoretical roots, which included publications conceptually draw from as a starting point for agency research and further conceptualizations.

4. Theoretical Roots

As *Figure 3* illustrates, agency-related research in the field stems from diverse theoretical backgrounds and, thus, different paradigms and ontological assumptions. This makes discussing key results challenging since one risks decoupling or oversimplifying different theories. To mitigate this, it is useful to take a closer look at some central theoretical roots directly concerned with agency that many of the included articles rely on first to account for some of the ontological differences before giving a conceptual synthesis.

Anthony Giddens' structuration theory and his conceptualization of agency are commonly utilized ontologies in sustainability transformation research across conceptual borders. In his seminal work, *The Constitution of Society* (1984), Giddens aims to overcome the – from his perspective – one-sided thought of functionalist and structuralist theory on one side, and individualist and hermeneutical subjectivist traditions on the other. The former would give deterministic primacy of action to structure while the latter side argues that structures are essentially independently and purposefully created by agents (pp. 1f.). Giddens tries to overcome this dichotomy with his theory of the duality of structure, which embeds agency in the process of structuration, where action is understood simultaneously as constrained and enabled by existing structures while reproducing or shaping/creating them.

⁵ Due to the usage of the word transformation in the search string instead of only using transitions, a broad range of journals are included (over 50 peer-reviewed journals and 3 other edited collections) with only 3 or less included articles per publication medium.

Figure 2. Descriptive Results.

Figure 3. Diverse Theoretical Backgrounds of Agency Concepts in Sustainability Transformation Research. This figure is a heuristic depiction of theoretical approaches and fields significantly drawn from as a conceptual starting point for agency research in the included publications. Since many publications employ multiple theories or schools of thought, up to three entries have been counted for each. While most theoretical approaches listed here can be associated with multiple and partially unmentioned disciplines, for simplicity, the primary ones have been selected for depiction. The grey category 'other' at the bottom left largely entails theory/approaches from economics, business- and management studies, innovation studies, design studies, and human geography.

In this context, Giddens scrutinizes the common definition of agency as intentional action-taking (meaning agents intending their action to have a certain effect) by arguing that this understanding of agency ties agency to the consequence of action without recognizing the necessity of power and knowledgeability. Giddens argues that “[a]gency refers not to the intentions people have in doing things but to their capability of doing those things in the first place” (p. 9), and hence, agency implies power. In his terms, agency is about agent-driven events where “the individual could, at any phase in a given sequence of conduct, have acted differently” (p. 9). Although this aspect of ‘could have acted otherwise’ is key to his concept and also is usually cited in the current literature (e.g., Avelino, 2017; Hoffman et al., 2021), it is only little discussed what this ‘could have’ really means and how far it goes.

While essentially agreeing with Giddens’ critique of the one-sided approaches to agency, **Margaret Archer** criticizes Giddens solution as analytically blurring the issue (1995, pp. 93ff.) since it conflates structure and agency, which, although interdependent, should be treated separately. She argues that processes of agency and structure should be analyzed using a periodical time frame that dissects their intermingled nature.⁶ However, Archer further stresses the active role of agents’ reflexivity, understood as the ability of people “to consider themselves in relation to their (social) contexts and vice versa” (Archer, 2007, p. 7) in agency⁷, which has been taken up in recent concepts (O’Brien et al., 2023). Reflexivity can be seen as the key mental and active-agential mode of relating individual action to the social context purposefully.

Giddens’ and Archer’s different perspectives essentially concern whether we can and should separate structure and agency, which is still a central ambiguous disagreement within the larger sustainability transformations literature on agency (see Section 5.2 Seven Questions on Agency Q3).

The literature also builds on multiple other perspectives with varying stances on this issue. One is **Albert Bandura’s** (1997, 2006) psychological conceptualization of agency in which agents’ psychological processes shaping their deliberate actions are articulated. Bandura’s theory of agency postulates four general characteristics—intentionality, forethought, self-reactiveness, and self-reflectiveness—which are all personal processes characterizing individual freedom of action (Bandura, 2006). In his view, agency is about agents’ ability to make plans, shape the situations they are in, and guide their overall pathways of life.

Conversely, **Emirbayer and Mische** (1998) propose a temporal and highly embedded notion of agency, defining it as a “temporally constructed engagement by actors of different structural environments [...] which, through the interplay of habit, imagination, and judgment, both reproduces and transforms those structures [...]” (ibid., p. 970). Crucial here are two things: the temporal construction of agency and the shift away from individual action to an actorial engagement. The former they articulate clearly by further distinguishing between

⁶ Archer does this with the concept of the morphogenetic-cycle (1995, pp. 247ff.), which, as well as her in broader work on agency and reflexivity, is not really applied or referred to in the sustainability transformations literature.

⁷ This understanding of agency contrasts Giddens’ understanding of reflexivity as a form of monitoring social life self-consciously – which is more passive, almost habitual compared to Archer’s more active definition.

three “constitutive elements of human agency” (ibid.): iteration (associated with routines, and habits rooted in the past), projectivity (associated with visions and narratives for the future), and practical evaluation (how past and future come evaluatively and consciously together in the present moment). The latter remains nebulous since they do not further conceptually explore what ‘engagement by actors’ really refers to and what types of action (e.g., also w.r.t. structural reproduction and intentionality) their notion of agency entails. Still, the temporal aspects they discuss are strongly represented (if not echoed) in current research of institutional practices (e.g., Friedrich et al., 2023; Wojtynia et al., 2023) on one hand, and visioning/futuring on the other (e.g., Bazzani, 2022), offering specific insights on bridging the two.

Turning now to **institutional work** which is a specific way of viewing agency in large parts of sustainability transition studies. Institutional work stems from organizational studies and was developed in Lawrence and Suddaby (2006) and Lawrence et al. (2009), and has been prominently advanced and related to Giddens’ structuration theory by Fuenfschilling and Truffer (2016). Institutional work refers to actions that (intentionally) “aim at the creation, maintenance or disruption of institutions” (Fuenfschilling & Truffer, 2016, p. 299). Approaches of institutional work are keen on describing and analyzing actors and their actions (as in strategies) specific to the institutional context they are embedded in, which is naturally intuitive and close to the defining endeavor of sustainability transition studies as in understanding and enabling socio-technical transitions. However, with regard to the deterministic nature of this institutional embeddedness of agency the concept remains ambiguous, occasionally converging to a structuralist view e.g. when Fuenfschilling and Truffer (2016) reflect about the role of intentionality in agency by stating on one side “actors are capable of engaging in purposeful behaviour” but on the other “what is considered rational and purposeful is shaped by the institutional environment” (p. 300). It could be argued that it is not the conceptual goal of institutional work to delve into the deeper determinisms of agency but more to focus on specific strategies that explain and hence can be applied to enable institutional disruption, maintenance, and creation to make sustainability transitions. Similar in this regard is also the regularly referred to eclectic notion of place-based agency by Grillitsch and Sotarauta (2020), combining Schumpeterian innovative and institutional entrepreneurship and place-based leadership theory.

Contrary to these embedded and applied notions of agency, an array of highly relational conceptualizations of so-called **distributed agency** should be mentioned here which particularly found application in social innovation theory (e.g., Pel et al., 2020a; 2020b). The distinctive feature of these notions being that agency is shared among multiple human or non-human agents, and hence, actions and related outcomes that may seem like individual agency are actually complex emergent phenomena resulting from an interplay of numerous forces of agency.

5. Interpretative Results

The inductive analysis revealed a great diversity in the field with regard to defining and characterizing agency, the question of what factors shape agency, and relationships to major concepts such as transition/transformation, structure, or power. As main interpretative result,

it is proposed to structure this complex debate by following seven key questions on agency research (see Section 5.2 Seven Questions on Agency). Additionally, it is argued that there are three prototypical perspectives on agency in the field, which are established in this article first (see Section 5.1 Three Prototypical Perspectives on Agency in Sustainability Transformation Research) to allow a clearer presentation.

5.1 Three Prototypical Perspectives on Agency in Sustainability Transformation Research

In this section, a heuristic typology of prototypical perspectives on agency is presented, which is based on the analysis that will be reported in Section 5.2 Seven Questions on Agency. The typology has been developed using the *criterion* of in how far deterministic primacy is given to the agent alone versus given to the relational interactivity of being and acting in a socio-material environment filled with engaging institutional structures as well as other human and non-human agents. It is proposed to distinguish between three prototypical perspectives: singular agency, embedded agency and relational/emergent agency (see *Figure 4*).

Singular Agency

Under singular agency approaches, perspectives on agency are subsumed, which see the agent as rather independent from the specific context the agent is embedded in regarding the determination of their (intentional) actions. Hence, while the agent of course interacts with their environment (e.g., via mobilizing resources), these interactions stem purely (or largely) from the intention and ability of the agent. The (intentional) actions of the agent are primarily formed by the agent's internal characteristics alone, only in reference to the environment. These characteristics can be motives, interests, knowledge, beliefs, skills or personality in case of a human agent, and organizational or leadership characteristics in the case of a corporate agent (see Q2).

Drawing on psychological, entrepreneurship, or social learning literature, archetypical publications taking such a singular agency perspective are, among others, Koistinen et al., (2020), Pekkanen (2021), Ruhrort and Allert (2021), Wilden and Feldmeyer (2021), Koistinen et al. (2022), Koskela and Paloniemi (2023), Wamsler et al. (2022, 2023) as well as, leaning slightly to embedded, Crivits and Paredis (2013), Benessiah and Eakin (2021) and Torre et al. (2020).

Embedded Agency

Embedded agency approaches see intentional actions more as stemming from an interactive process between the agents' characteristics and the causal or suggestive effects of the structural context the agent is embedded in *on* the agent. Therefore, agency is also shaped in strong reference to the socio-material system the agent is embedded in, but not only on a knowledge or strategic level (e.g. by the agent analyzing the system), as would be the case for singular agency approaches, but also on the basis of a) normative & incentivization expectations that the structural context suggests, and b) the available resources, means, and power the structure allows for the agent.

Archetypal publications are de Haan and Rotmans' (2018) framework for actors in transformative change, de Roeck and Van Poeck's (2023) transactional pragmatism, Madsen et al.'s (2022) theory of contestation axes, as well as approaches based on Lewin's field theory (Kump, 2023) or strategic action field theory (Kungl & Hess, 2021).

Some approaches can be put more in between the singular and embedded category, such as most studies on institutional work (Novalia et al., 2018, 2020; Beunen & Patterson, 2019), institutional entrepreneurship (Heiskanen et al., 2019) or place-based agency (Sotarauta et al., 2021; Sotarauta & Grillitsch, 2023).

Relational or Emergent Agency

Relational or emergent agency approaches are very diverse, but they take agency and also (intentional) action-taking per se more as a phenomenon that is patterned or emerges as a result of a process of various interacting agents, often including non-human agents and their various relationally conditioned characteristics. The unit of analysis is often a network of interactions between these different agents, usually stemming from concepts of distributed agency, actor-network theory, or poststructuralist thought. Archetypal publications are Charli-Joseph et al. (2018, 2023), Jokinen et al. (2021), Hirvensalo et al. (2021), Kok et al. (2021), and Tàbara (2023).

Figure 4. Conceptual synthesis of diverse perspectives on agency in sustainability transformation research.

5.2 Seven Questions on Agency

Table 1 shows the adapted questioning scheme developed as a result of the explorative coding phase as well as the estimated state of the literature. Key interpretative results are reported for each of the questions in the following.

No.	Question	Status of the literature
Q1	How can agency be <i>defined</i> ? (What is agency?)	implicitly debated / diverse & partially contradictory
Q2	What is the presumed <i>source of agency</i> ? (Where does agency lie? How is it constituted?)	elaborate & diverse perspectives
Q3	What is the specific relationship of agency to <i>sustainability transition/transformation</i> ?	implicit
Q4	What is the relationship of agency and <i>structure</i> ?	debated & partially contradictory
Q5	What is the relationship of agency and <i>power</i> ? (What is the exact difference?)	underdeveloped / unclear
Q6	What are determining or <i>shaping factors of the normative quality</i> of agency, and also, of exercised agency?	underdeveloped / unclear
Q7	What is expected of a <i>theory of agency</i> ? (What does and doesn't it explain? What does it help?)	implicitly debated

Table 1. Proposed seven key questions on agency – based on the first explorative coding phase and applied as a coding tool for all included articles.

Q1 Definition.

Despite the generally shared understanding that agency is about agents and their actions, there is no consensus on the exact definition and meaning of agency within the broader research community. This lack of consensus is highlighted in Table 2, which presents a selection of definitions of agency from the included articles, each associated with a key distinguishing attribute and the prototypical perspective (singular, embedded, or relational/emergent).

First, there is an inconsistency in whether agency should be viewed merely as taking (some form of) action or if it encompasses – as typical in philosophy (see Ferrero, 2021) – the broader capability of taking action. What this capability analytically captures is a key distinguishing feature of whether the perspective is more singular, embedded, or relational/emergent. Second, there is the question of whether and to which extent to include some form of intentionality or purposefulness in the definition, which characterizes the type of actions deemed agential. Third, the definitions diverge on whether agency addresses merely action or in how far it includes extends of effect or consequence. This is a distinction that significantly influences the scope of agency. Lastly, some recent publications, usually drawing on Actor-Network-Theory, include non-human entities as agents capable of exerting agency into the definition, reflecting and expanding the boundaries of what constitutes agency and where it lies or emerges.

While this diversity in definitions, in a way, mirrors the pertinent conceptual richness of the different theoretical backgrounds researchers draw from, it also poses challenges not only for coming to a shared minimal understanding of what agency is but also hinders the cumulative development of deeper characterizations or theories of agency. Further, it cannot be said that an explicit debate is going on within the broader research community about which definition (not to talk about characterization/theory yet) would be more useful. This problem, as well as the difficulty of comparing studies on agency, is exacerbated by publications omitting to clarify what their understanding of agency is, although being decidedly and conceptually about agency (see *Figure 2*).

Definition Type	Examples	Suggested Agency Perspective
Only Action	"agency (i.e. the making of independent choices by actors)" (Grin et al., 2011, p. 3)	Singular Agency
+ Intentionality	"Agency means to "influence intentionally one's functioning and life circumstances. [...]" (Bandura, 2006, p. 164)" (Buhr et al. 2023, p. 4223)	Singular Agency
+ Effect & Consequence	"human agency refers to "intentional, purposive and meaningful actions, and the intended and unintended consequences of such actions" (Grillitsch and Sotarauta, 2020, p. 707)." (Roebke et al., 2022)	Singular / Embedded Agency
Ability / Capability / Capacity to Action	"capacity to choose and pursue a course of action" (Adams, 2021, p. 10)	Singular Agency
	"Agency refers to the ability to act, to make one's own free choices in hopes of changing one's life circumstances" (Benessiah & Eakin 2021, p. 1843)	Singular Agency
+ Intentionality	"We understand agency as the ability to act with intention – as opposed to just reacting" (de Haan & Rotmans, 2018, p. 4)	Embedded Agency (as rooted in their concept of agency)
+ Intentionality / Reflexivity	"we approach agency as the culturally and historically contingent capacity of actors "to interpret and morally evaluate their situation and to formulate projects and try to enact them" (Ortner 1995: 185) – both individually and collectively" (Hölscher et al., 2023, p. 5)	Embedded Agency
+ Intentionality / Effect	"Human agency can be defined as the capacity to change systems through conscious actions " (O'Brien, 2023, p. 1449)	Agency as Relational / Emergent
+ Non-Human Agency	"Hence, from this relational nondualistic perspective, agency is understood as the capacity to influence the interactions of others, but where these 'others' also include non-human actants (cf Latour) that affect human agents' motives, socioenvironmental practices, and system' structuring forces." (Tàbara et al., 2023, p. 369)	Agency as Relational / Emergent
Different	"actors' agency—conceived as the meanings and means behind (re)actions" (Lundsgaard-Hansen et al., 2018, p. 1)	Singular / Embedded Agency
	"Agency is defined as "the relation between a person and a course of action and its effects (Enfield and Kockelman, 2017, p. 7)." (Engez et al., 2021, p. 293)	Agency as Relational / Emergent
Vague/Implicit	"agency arises from the ability to enrol others" (Heiskanen et al., 2018, p. 3)	Singular / Embedded Agency
	"The problem of agency involves questions like: what is or can be the contribution of actors to transitions; how can this role be theoretically captured; and how can agents influence or contribute to a transition process?" (Pesch, 2015, p. 379)	Embedded Agency

Table 2. Examples for definitions of agency. There are several key distinguishing attributes between the selected definitions (while not being an exhaustive list, it was tried to select the most representative examples for distinguishing attributes).

Q2 Source & Location.

The question of source (i.e., where the capability for action actually stems from), as well as location (i.e., where the agent with crucial agency is located), are most intensely studied in the literature. Key commonalities and differences in source and location are reported for each of the three prototypical perspectives of agency.

For more *singular agency* approaches, the source of agency is largely understood as lying in the *internal* characteristics of the agent. Key human-individual internal agency characteristics (which may overlap to some degree and relate to the corresponding conceptualizations) are:

- Knowledge/competence (e.g., system-knowledge, knowledge of strategies) (Colloff et al., 2021; Wilden & Feldmeyer, 2021), beliefs (such as perceived self-efficacy or trust) and emotions (Wamsler et al., 2022, 2023).
- preferences, attitudes, values (Bögel & Upham, 2018; Pekkanen, 2021; Pahl-Wostl et al., 2023; Plüschke-Altöf et al., 2023) and internalized social norms (Ibrahim, 2017; Ruhrort & Allert, 2021; Upham et al., 2021)
- perceptions (Halinski & Duxbury, 2020; Wamsler et al., 2022, 2023)
- personality (Crivits & Paredis, 2013; Antadze & McGowan, 2017; Vasquez-Delsolar & Merino, 2021)
- skills, abilities, or practical competencies to exert certain strategies (Novalia et al., 2018, 2020; Torre et al., 2020; Roebke et al., 2022; Buhr et al., 2023; Friedrich et al., 2023)

Some publications emphasize that agency (since internally characterized) directly is constituted by complex forms of (social-) learning (Stetsenko, 2019; Stocco et al., 2021; Koskela & Paloniemi, 2023; tangentially also Pesch et al., 2017). This issue of learning is discussed with regard to not only enabling agents to do what they want to do but also to allow agents to actually learn to know what they may want to do – generating ideas for sustainable involvement (Lotz-Sisitka et al., 2017; Probst et al., 2019; Budowle et al., 2021).

The role of the *ability to use or relate these characteristics to the specific contextuality the agent is in*, e.g., by acting with reference to specific windows of opportunities, is regularly emphasized, and often based on the usage of various types of resources available at hand (Colloff et al., 2021) or also, by conciliating and collaborating in networks (Ibrahim, 2017).

Embedded conceptualizations of agency do not deny these internal characteristics highlighted and often explicitly integrate these in their frameworks. However, additional emphasis as a source of agency is put on how the contextual conditions interact and shape the actions or the capability for action of certain agents. Different researchers take different foci in this regard on what role the external plays here.

For example, De Haan and Rotmans (2018) is basing agency on value streams which can rise or dry up, being not – as would be the perspective of singular approaches – values one agent has (and which may be shared by other agents), but more values which are picked up collectively and are structurally/conditionally upheld. Conversely, Westley et al.'s (2013) transformative agency approach sees the source of 'successful' agency in the competence of strategic correspondence, of linking the system's status (following Holling's adaptive cycle)

and tailored strategies, particularly exploiting windows of opportunities. Similarly, which could also be interpreted as some form of strategic correspondence, Pesch (2015) frames agency particularly in the context of disposing over discursive space: when agents have the capability to interfere in existing discursive spaces, or creating new ones, then it is argued they have a capability of changing system pathways.

More recent literature stresses agency being inherently affected by capabilities of (social-) resource mobilization and characteristics of existing social networks (Duygan et al., 2019; Yu & Gibbs, 2020; Strasser et al., 2022; Friedrich et al., 2023), some also reflecting on the shaping nature of actor-interactions on agency in general (De Herde et al., 2019; De Roeck & Van Poeck, 2023). Approaches drawing on Dorado (2005) or also Emirbayer & Mische's (1998) theory of agency rely on existing, previously formed practices in interaction with future-oriented visions/aims and narratives as being a defining driver of agency.

Some research articulates that (institutional) spaces can allow or foster agency. Bögel et al. (2022) see space as "the container for agency" (p. 171) and Charli-Joseph et al. (2018, 2023) examine how specific experimental spaces allow agency to emerge. The source of agency is – at least analytically – emphasized as driven from the spatial and conditional context.

Relational or emergent agency approaches go much further in emphasizing the interactive nature of agents and their context, attributing the source of agency to complex interactive networks of human and non-human relationships. It is argued that analytically, there is no way of putting the finger on a general class of factors which shape emergent agency phenomena. Arora et al. (2023) argue that agency is "constituted by [agents'] relations with nature and technology" (p. 2), while agency always remaining underdetermined since "relational effects are emergent" (p. 8).

Relational approaches with an explicitly not-only-human agency approach tend to remain rather agnostic to the explicit source of agency. Whereas Kok et al. (2021) theorize agency, understood as the "capacity for reorientation" (p. 1) of (networks of) human and non-human components, as patterned by structures and external agency, the *remaining* source of this capacity for reorientation is not further explained. Jokinen et al. (2021) describe the process more generally as a cyclical movement of changing non-human/human relational interactions, without claiming any explicit source as well.

Q3 Agency & Transformation.

The link between agency and the transformative process is usually assumed implicitly (as agency to change something towards sustainability) but also depends largely on the characterization of agency (Q1). More specifically, the connection between agency and the transformative process is largely suggested or analyzed with reference to specific frameworks or theories, such as in institutional work (Fuenfschilling & Truffer, 2016; Beunen & Patterson, 2019; Hoffman et al., 2021), building adaptive capacities (Bettini et al., 2015), transformative capacities (Wolfram, 2016) or governance (Hernandez & Schanz, 2019; Salman & Mori, 2023).

The tie between agency and transformative processes is sometimes also explicated via theorizing about specific agents and actions/strategies. For example, taking the definition of institutional work "as those actions through which actors attempt to, or in effect do, create,

maintain, or disrupt institutional structures” (Beunen & Patterson, 2019, p. 23), agency is directly linked to a *specific* understanding of the transformational process. Consequently, different strategies can be associated to each of the attempted kind or phase of institutional work (Novalia et al., 2018) and are then discussed as different kinds of agency.

Within another paradigm, Brodnik and Brown (2018) distinguish between different capacity-building phases and locate agency within them, whereas Strasser (2022) structures agency more w.r.t. specific roles and strategies associated with desired transformational outcomes. Wolfram (2016) patterns agency across various scales and levels and conceives agency as an integral aspect of essentially all other components required to allow building transformative capacities.

Coming from a social practices perspective focussing on the individual in relation to the performed reality they are embedded in, De Roeck and Van Poeck (2023) see agency as the crucial means to interrupt existing social practices, which, is argued to enable transformative change by altering old or creating novel practices. Whereas Pel et al. (2020a), putting more attention on the collective and coming from a social innovations view, link a strongly distributed notion of agency to the transformative process understood as shifting social relations. The link between agency and the transformative process is very much tied to the specific theoretical framework and ontology deployed in the analysis.

Throughout the literature, regularly the assumption is made that if certain agents would have been given more agency (or if they could unfold their agency better), then transformative change towards sustainability would be amplified (de Haan & Rotmans, 2018; Koistinen et al., 2018; Hoppe, 2021; Plüschke-Altöf et al., 2023) and also participatorially/democratically be more just (Gram-Hanssen, 2021; O’Brien et al., 2023). Consequentially, it is argued that certain structures should be changed or construed in order to improve the agency of agents (e.g. Hirth et al., 2023).

Q4 Agency & Structure.

The question of the relationship between agency and structure is a foundational and ontological one, controversially debated across disciplines and also in general agency theorizing (see Section

Theoretical Roots). Great and diverse discussions in the context of sustainability transformations can be found in Hausknot (2014), Stirling (2014), De Roeck & Van Poeck (2023), Kok et al. (2021) and Kok (2023).

In the present interpretation of the literature, this question clearly distinguishes the singular, embedded, and relational typology (as is also shown in Q2). In general, there is a broad agreement that structure essentially limits and enables agency in various ways. However, singular agency approaches see this structured environment more as the situation in which the agent acts in rather independently, e.g., by being subjected to certain structural logics or constraints (Benessaiah & Eakin, 2021; Vasquez-Delsolar & Merino, 2021) whereas in more embedded or relational approaches, structure impacts agency directly and inherently (e.g., in action field theory via field forces, Kungl & Hess, 2021; Kump, 2023). This is taken to various degrees and very much depends on the explicit approach.

In more relational approaches, structures are sometimes seen as uncertain indeterminacies emerging fluidly within assemblages (Arora et al., 2023). Others reject the agency-structure distinction fully and directly (Jokinen et al., 2021; Tàbara, 2023).

Kok et al. (2021) see structure (in the context of a complex adaptive systems perspective) as those networks of components “[...] forming the conditions of agency – i.e. as constituting components’ capacity for reorientation. These structures may be rules, habits, routines, cultures but also materiality, ecology, technology etc.” (p. 5). Particularly due to their unique understanding of agency (as a capacity of (networks of) human and non-human agents for reorientation), this is an interesting turn on the structure-agency debate, since it distinguishes in a way between the ‘free’ (in the sense of internally alterable) and ‘non-free’ configurations in a network and points at how their free action space is shaped via other structuring components exerting power (see Q5).

Q5 Agency & Power.

Agency and power are intuitively strongly related, not only since agency in the context of transformative processes may challenge power relations (Heiskanen et al., 2018; Benessaiah & Eakin, 2021) but also, since processes of (dis-)empowerment shape whose agency impacts what and whom how in the end (Madsen et al., 2022; Pel, 2020a; Pel, 2020b). However, the exact relationship of agency and power remains often blurry or purely implicit, and only few publications tackle both concepts simultaneously and their link in detail.

In general, power is largely seen as an integral part of agency via the capability of mobilizing people and resources, or having the means to achieve a goal (Benessaiah & Eakin, 2018). Agents without power either do not really have agency, or their agency does not count (Lundsgaard-Hansen et al., 2018). It is often suggested that only those who have power or access to power can actually create an impact (Upham & Gather, 2021; Salman & Mori, 2023; van Dokkum et al., 2023).

In some conceptualizations, the focus is less placed on power as a means of agency, but more on agency requiring to navigate or “to attune to power dynamics” (Budowle et al., 2021, p. 5) in order to be effective, hence viewing it more ‘structural’. Similarly, De Haan and Rotmans (2018) link it to positionality by stating that not everyone is in a position to change something.

Since Avelino (2017) and Kok et al. (2021) have the most explicit and in-depth conceptualizations of power and agency, some space is taken here to examine their understandings. A big conceptual difference stems, however, from the different notions of agency they conceive.

Avelino (2017) gives a comprehensive conceptualization of different kinds of power(s), which, as she states, are largely “agency-based notions of power” (ibid. p. 5). Without giving a clear concept of agency herself (besides referring to Giddens’ notion of agency as acting otherwise), her dialectical notion of power as “the (in)capacity of actors to mobilize resources and institutions to achieve a goal” (ibid. p. 3) is quite close to how many authors view agency. The different mobilizable resource types Avelino mentions (mental, human, artefactual, natural and monetary) to exercise power are largely part of the internal and external

characteristics mentioned for enabling agency in singular and embedded approaches. However, Avelino (2017) puts a stronger emphasis on the relational nature of power (e.g. who has power over whom or who has more/less power, which could be interpreted as relations of interacting agencies of different agents). Further, she argues that power largely “resides in the social context (Barnes, [1988]2002: 127) and actors ‘possess power only in so far as they are relationally constituted as doing so’ (Clegg, [1989] 2002: 257)” (Avelino, 2017, p. 4). Specifically, in locating different types of power within the MLP and characterizing empowerment, Avelino (2017) makes a huge contribution to understanding better which types and shapes agency can take and how these relationally interact in the form of power relations within various qualitatively different contexts in transition processes. However, although Avelino directly illustrates how closely knit power is to agency, with regard to the exact and distinct relationship between the two concepts, she remains rather agnostic.

Conversely to seeing power as a means for agency, more relational approaches, such as Kok et al. (2021) see power more distinctly as structuring the conditions agency takes place or emerges in (similar in this assumption are Jokinen et al., 2021; Charli-Joseph et al., 2018, 2023; Tàbara, 2023; Arora et al., 2023). As suggested briefly in Q4, Kok et al. (2021) describe power as “emerg[ing] from interactions” (p. 6) with an “intensity as well as a directionality (Stirling, 2019)” (p. 6) which “structur[es] agency” (p. 6) via impacts on social relationships, practices, and institutional arrangements. These conditions for agency, are impacted by either structures or other agents and their agency (including non-humans and networks). This understanding of power is, in principle, not so different from Avelino’s, but a conceptual explication and augmentation to non-humans of agency as conditioned by power.

Notable in this context is also Jokinen et al.’s (2021) depiction of the power of non-human agents over other agents. They take the simple example of asbestos by describing it as having significant power over humans because of its “material properties, capacities, and affordances” (p. 309). Via this power, the agency of other agents (e.g. a human agent in a chemistry lab) is structured. Although this understanding of agency and power is quite general and erases the role of intentionality completely from the concept, it shows quite clearly how networks of components enable and constrain each other.

Q6 Agency Normative Quality Determinants.

While processes enabling or restraining agency are largely discussed in the literature, there is only little research specifically addressing what actually shapes the normative direction of performed agency. In most studies, it is implicitly assumed that if certain agents have more agency or can act more freely, then they will likely act towards a more sustainable system or society as a whole. Factors identified to affect the capability of taking action (Q2) are also reasonably shaping the normative direction of intention and the kind of actions taken in the end. Quality determinants listed here are usually just mentioned in the described context, but the exact relationships between these factors and the normative direction of the performed agency are rarely studied in sustainability transformation research – at least under the agency label. It is distinguished between a) aspects shaping the normative orientation of agency and b) aspects shaping the success, outcome, or performance of actions with regard to implicit sustainability transformations criteria.

a) *Aspects shaping the normative orientation.* Among more singular approaches (and also some embedded), emphasis is put on the aims or objectives of agents (Andriamihaja et al., 2021; Plüschke-Altöf et al., 2023), which agents are assumed to be having internally and analytically ex-ante. Others take into account that such aims as drivers of agency are rooted in a variety of psychological concepts, such as values, beliefs, perceptions, attitudes, desires (compare Q2), but also mindsets (Ruhrt & Allert, 2021), the force of wanting to reduce conflict (Kump, 2023), or norms and culture in general (Upham et al., 2021). Learning and education are discussed as a key driver as well, not only by helping to integrate information and value orientations but also by shaping a person's beliefs (Wolfgramm et al., 2015; van Poeck et al., 2017). Such characteristics can also be analyzed from a life-course perspective (Koistinen et al., 2020). The role of perceived risk and uncertainties in interaction with other factors are also highlighted by some as shaping characteristics of agency (e.g., Groves et al., 2016; Colloff et al., 2021; Upham et al., 2021). This is exemplified in detail in the context of farmers' struggle for change (Friedrich et al., 2023), or the context of projective reasoning (Bazzani, 2022). Although only occasionally hinted at, reflexivity can be seen as key for integrating these different shaping aspects consciously (e.g., Novalia et al., 2018, 2020).

b) *Aspects shaping the success, outcome, or performance.* Since outcome is a key explanandum for sustainability transformation research, generally more explicit emphasis is put on this part of Q6. Much research drawing on case studies derives particular characteristics of strategies and interventions (or explicit strategies in the first place) that are likely to be effective in bringing sustainability change processes forward. Studying these strategies or actions, which are often also portrayed in certain actor roles, are then associated with the label 'agency'. Such strategies are largely context-specific and cannot all be listed here (some notable examples in general are (Brown et al., 2013; Werbeloff et al., 2016; Brodnik & Brown, 2018; Heiskanen et al., 2018; Arenas et al., 2020; Chaminade & Randelli, 2020; Ramirez et al., 2020; Gram-Hanssen, 2021; Sotarauta et al., 2021; Strasser et al., 2022).

Overall, the lack of explicitly addressing how certain characteristics do not only shape agency in magnitude, but also in quality may be an issue, particularly when examining not only the agency of the often so-called change agent but also the agency of resistant forces with other, conflicting normative goals.

Q7 Agency-Theory.

A fundamental discussion threads through the literature implicitly, which is about *what should* an agency theory actually *explain* on one side and, in a second step, *provide* for bringing sustainability transformation research forward.

Within the literature, there are different perspectives on what agency-related research is actually about. While it is clear, and has been discussed broadly already that most agency research is rooted in some theoretical foundation or applied framework, the actual meta-questions concerned when zooming out across paradigms are not always the same. Coding suggests three main distinct, but often overlapping aspects with some outliers.

a) *Describing actions or interactions within specific contexts.* Even though agency is often defined as some sort of capability, agency-related research, often drawing on case studies or agent typologies, tends to have the aim to more describe actions w.r.t. the theory of change

applied (and not so much to explain the capability per se, compare also Q3). The description of the agency is, therefore, some kind of micro-foundation of the process (as argued as being conceptually necessary over a decade ago by Geels, 2020; Grin et al., 2011) and largely descriptive, with prescriptive outcomes suggested. For literature drawing on actor-network theory, this also tends to be the case when analyzing complex networks of interactions.

b) Informing the performance of change agency. In a way, an extension of a), agency-related research focussing more specifically on informing successful change agency are abundant (compare Q6b). The question of anticipated outcome, or also which specific characteristics (e.g., abilities, skills, knowledge) a certain agent needs to possess to enable change are studied.

c) Showing how agency (as a capability) is acquired, shaped and structured. This is basically debated most by the literature which concerns Q2 but also Q4-Q6. It is about understanding how to build this capability but also understanding essentially the reasons for certain actions.

The issue with all three a), b), and c) is also that there is no coherent distinction with what type of actions are addressed. This is where the distinction of talking about intentional (or 'free' or deliberate) action versus just any action or 'change action' becomes crucial. However, throughout the literature there is no clear consensus on the question of which types of action we talk about when talking about agency. Even in cases of defining agency explicitly being about intentional action, there is rarely clarified what actions can be seen why as intentional. This makes the debate fuzzy, particularly w.r.t. the agency-structure debate, as, for example, routinious actions relate very differently to structure as intentional ones.

6. Discussion

As shown, in the rapidly evolving, highly interdisciplinary field of sustainability transformation and transition studies, conceptualizations on agency are incredibly diverse, are based on a variety of theoretical backgrounds, and have been applied in an array of different empirical contexts. Previous calls for a clearer and deeper understanding of agency in change processes, along with the rapidly increasing number of publications on the topic, underscore the pertinent interest in grasping agency better. However, while diversity in theory is crucial to not only bring debate forward but also to have applicable frameworks at hand which can be applied and correspond to the key empirical questions in the field, some shared understanding, as well as synthesis of concepts, is essential too in order to gain more consistency, comparability, and depth.

A key issue at the root of agency debates is (as results for Q1, Q7 directly, and also Q3 suggest), that it is not so much clear of which kinds of actions we are talking about. This entails not only the issue of whether it is just about all agency or as is assumed often implicitly about *change* agency, but even more so whether we talk about *any* action, as e.g., also actors perform as part of their structurally governed role, or whether we only talk about actions which could be seen as *free*, as e.g., an agent may be assumed to perform, as a leader of their own life. This issue of 'about which action do we talk?' can be seen as being about whether and how to include intentionality in a definition of agency. Clarifying this is crucial particularly for understanding change – because sustainable change is exactly about

overcoming the harmful existing ways of doing (i.e. the default and structurally led actions) by finding ways of how it is possible *to stop the stable reproduction* of these harmful practices, *to do differently* until a more sustainable enactment is created and normalized (Shove & Walker, 2010; Haslanger, 2022; Spatan et al., 2024). A conceptualization of agency needs to capture and not blur this distinction which lies in the way structure is being understood as part of agency or not.

To clarify this crucial role of intentionality in the definition of agency, an adaptation of existing agency definitions is proposed and elaborated:

Definition. Agency is the capability (of an agent) to perform intentional action (as a result of some *reflective deliberation*) within/with reference to specific spatio-temporal contexts.

This definition is tailored to correspond particularly to singular and embedded approaches focussing on an understanding of human agency, and less to relational/emergent ones (see discussion below). The proposed definition has essentially four components: *capability*, *intention*, *performance*, and *locale*.

Capability is referring to both the conception and performance of the intentional action the agent came up with as suitable from their view w.r.t. the specific spatio-temporal context they are situated in. Further, the usage of the word capability (instead of ability or capacity) is meant as including both the internal ability of an agent, as well as their external power (as in lying in the contextual properties for the agent, such as the access to mobilizing resources, conditions of networks, aspects of legitimacy). Subsequently, *performance* is referring to the enactment of the intentional action the agent consciously decided for and is linked to the agent's specific spatio-temporal context (*locale*). This locale is structured by the socio-material conditions via shaping the spatio-temporal realities the agent is situated in as well as their corresponding perceptions, governing correspondingly the set of available actions the agent possibly could perform, as well as the ones the agent consciously construes as possible and reasonable to perform (compare Hausknot, 2014 for a discussion on *decision* as a key agential operator).

Intentionality is a more complex issue and has been part of extensive debates not only in philosophy (Jacob, 2023) but also directly in sociology concerning agency (e.g., Giddens, 1984; Sewell, 1992; B. Barnes, 2000). In my understanding of intentionality, it is about a 'will' to achieve or perform something that stems from the agent's own thoughts, beliefs, and values, being somewhat separate from the immediate influence of the agent's socio-material or structural situatedness. This is ontologically a difficult topic since, of course, thoughts, beliefs, and values, even arguably 'the will,' stem from the environment and culture we grow up or live in. Without being capable to theoretically dissect fully what is agent and what is structure here, a necessary heuristic might be that thoughts, beliefs and values have to be *manifested* within an agent to be called their own in the upper sense. Therefore, a kind-of situational constancy is at play – the agent holds certain thoughts, beliefs and values throughout time and space, throughout various situational contexts and thus, actions based on those manifest attributes (via a process of reflective deliberation) are actions concerning agency.

Another issue of intentionality, regularly omitted, is what the intention is actually about.⁸ When Giddens (1984) criticizes the role of intention via exclaiming that no agent really knows what the outcome of their action will be (see pp. 8ff.) and therefore, the intention of actions would sociologically not really matter as much, particularly for understanding agency, he omits fully that intention can also be about the *process of action*. There is a severe difference between intending an outcome and intending an act or a performance due to its characteristics (which is the key distinction between consequentialist and deontological ethics). The latter is about agents doing something intentionally because the performance may be seen as the right thing to do or also because it may create something desirable experientially during the act. There are deeply ethical, emotional, and experiential components in this intention of performance of action, which as a whole is overlooked. When talking about actions having to be intentional (in order to be about agency and not about structure) it is meant that the action has to be consciously decided for – on the basis of whatever reason, which not only has to be an outcome.

This process of intentionally deciding creatively *for* something may be best described with a process of reflective deliberation. Characterizing the deliberation process is a challenging task and there are probably a variety of different types and intensities of deliberation also interacting with structural forces. As a starting point for discussion, the following characterization is proposed:

Reflective deliberation (about performing an action) is a process of mindful contemplation about what and how to do, which takes

- own *internal* characteristics, such as beliefs, values, goals, interests, abilities, skills, knowledge, and emotions, on one side
- and *external* characteristics, such as available resources, general norms, institutional conditions, as well as the specific action context, others' actions & agency, etc., on the other

synthetically into account.

Further, it should be elaborated that the deliberation process does *not necessarily* have to be immediately tied to the action since it can have temporal, spatial, and even thematic distance. For example, if someone decides to eat vegan (as a result of some form of reflective deliberation and not because a social group strongly incentivizes them to do so), then the future acts of the person eating vegan meals are a result of this *distant* deliberation process.

This definition of individual agency distinguishes clearly between actions purely, unquestioningly governed by structures, from actions stemming from the reflective and integrating agent – without excluding the effect of structure on the decision and performance of the intentional action from agency. It aims to capture the capability of an agent to act in reflexive correspondence right in the situation they are in, applying the values and competencies they carry.

⁸ According to the Routledge Encyclopedia of Philosophy, “[i]ntentionality is the mind’s capacity to direct itself on things” (Crane, 2016), so the directedness of intentionality is seen as the defining characteristic (Jacob 2003).

In principle, I see this definition of agency close to Sewell's (1992) conception (as agents being "capable of exerting some degree of control over the social relations in which one is enmeshed" (p. 20) but also to frameworks such as Novalia et al. (2018) and Andrijeida (2021), which distinguish similarly between the internal and external characteristics shaping an agents' agency. However, a stronger emphasis is put here on intentionality and also reflexivity (as particularly highlighted by Margaret Archer) in using this internal capacity by drawing on those characteristics and synthetically combining them.

This definition is not meant as opposing or criticising relational or non-human agency approaches at all. Based on the research question and also underlying paradigm, different views on agency can be valuable. Particularly when looking at complex network interactions or also the distribution of agency it may be useful to take not such an individual-centric lens as suggested here (see also Teerikangas et al., 2021 about the different usage of agency approaches).

7. Further Research, Limitations and Concluding Remarks

Agency is a foundational unit of analysis for the purpose of sustainability transformation research and has been discussed diversely in the field and beyond. In this systematic-narrative review a comprehensive account of the state of the art of agency conceptualizations has been given. Distinguishing between three prototypical perspectives on agency – singular, embedded, and relational/emergent agency approaches, the debate has been structured using seven questions on agency, discussing issues around definition, source, location, and shaping characteristics of agency, as well as conceptual relations to structure, transition/transformation and power.

While comprehensive insights can be drawn on the source of agency across the literature, the overall lack of clarity and shared understanding of what agency actually is and what agency theory should be about still needs to be explicitly problematized and resolved in the debate of diverging conceptions – this review being only a starting point. On this basis, clearer relationships may be conceptually articulated to existing theories of transformative processes, as well as other key concepts such as power. Largely unaddressed remains the issue of *multiple intersecting agencies* of different agents. There is a tendency, particularly of singular and embedded approaches, to look only at the agency of the change agent who tries to illicit transformative change (notable expectations are Madsen et al., 2022; Kump, 2023).

Similarly, the crucial question of *collective agency* could only sparsely be addressed in this review due to the absence of clear theoretical development in the publications included within the scope of this review (notable exceptions are Ibrahim, 2017 and Charli-Joseph et al. 2023). This shall not suggest that sustainability transformations research is not examining the actions of collectives and how they emerge since particularly initiatives or social movements and their collective action are key topics of study in the field. The results of this review suggest that theorizing on collective action is quite disconnected to explicit theorizing on agency within the literature. It is crucial to bring existing concepts of agency closer to theory on collective action or even develop a solid notion of collective agency.

Three main limitations of this narrative-systematic review should be highlighted: First, although unavoidable due to the choice of methodology and style of the review, it should be mentioned that naturally substantial author subjectivity is involved in the interpretation of the literature as well as the selective presentation of results here. Second, with the conceptual synthesis comes the risk of decontextualization of individual results. This was tried to account for to some degree by discussing crucial individual publications explicitly and not only giving cumulated results. Third, this review has been mainly focussed on the definition and characterization of agency as a concept, and the diversity of agent/actor and agency types could only be sparsely explored due to the limited scope.

The derived reading of current conceptualizations of agency in sustainability transformations research, as well as the proposed characterization of human-agency as rooted in processes of reflective deliberation, can only be seen as a starting point for understanding transformative change constituting on an individual level more clearly. Surely, substantial social change is always made collectively, but it is sparked with individual agency pointing at various creative forms of collective organizing. Combining such a rather 'zoomed in on the agent' conception with the more macroscopic, highly relational/emergent approaches, may lead to a more comprehensive and multifaceted understanding of transformative collective agency in future research.

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Supplementary Material

The following supplementary material are provided for this article: 1) A list of all formally included articles (coded as highly and medium relevant) and 2) a .RIS data file including the original dataset of 1664 publications (duplicates removed).

Declaration of Generative AI and AI-assisted Technologies in the Writing Process

During the preparation of this work the author used ChatGPT4o in order to improve the language and flow of this article. After using this tool, the author reviewed and edited the content as needed and takes full responsibility for the content of the published article.

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